

In 1984-86 trials, the line yielded consistently higher than NN3A and NN6A (Table 1). It is moderately resistant to blast and brown planthopper

biotype 2 and susceptible to bacterial blight and sheath blight (Table 2).

In 1986, IR18348-36-3-3 was named OM89 by the Ministry of Agriculture

and released for large-scale cultivation in the Mekong Delta. IR18348-36-3-3, was released by the Philippine Seed Board as IR64 in 1985. □

Metica 1 released in Brazil

P.H.N. Rangel, E.P. Guimarães and V. dos A. Cutrim, National Research Center for Rice and Beans (EMBRAPA/CNPAF) - Caixa Postal 179, 74000 Goiânia, Goiás, Brazil

Irrigated rice is about 30% of the total area planted to rice in Brazil and 40% of total rice production. The most important areas for irrigated rice are located in the south, but lately emphasis has been placed on developing varieties for the tropical region.

In 1981, the National Research Center for Rice and Beans (EMBRAPA/CNPAF) introduced Metica 1 from the International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT), Cali, Colombia. Beginning in 1982, this variety was evaluated in several Brazilian states and in 1986 was released for commercial use in four states.

Average yields of Metica 1 were 14 – 50% higher than local checks' (see table), with similar grain quality. However, Metica 1 was found to be susceptible to brown spot and rice blast, primarily where water control was not adequate. The figure shows the area currently planted to irrigated rice in the states where Metica 1 was released. □

Area (ha) planted to irrigated rice in states where Metica 1 was released, Goiania, Brazil.

Days to flowering and grain yield of Metica 1.^a Goiânia, Brazil.

State	Days to flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)			Yield increase (%)
		Metica 1	Cica 8 (check)	De Abril (check)	
Rio de Janeiro (RJ)	115	4.9	–	4.3	14
Piauí (PI)	80	6.9	6.0	–	16
Goiás (Go)	90–115	8.0	6.7	–	19
Mato Grosso (MT)	95	6.2	4.1	–	50
Mean (PI, GO, MT)	–	7.0	5.6	–	25

^aAv of 29 trials.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization GERMPLASM

A simple and convenient method to preserve seed of rice germplasm

Chang-Xiang Mao, Hunan Hybrid Rice Research Center, Changsha, Hunan, China

More than 500 samples of rice seed harvested in autumn 1976 were sealed with indicating silica gel in glass ampules (see figure). The sealed ampules were

sorted in boxes placed in an ordinary room where the average monthly temperatures are about 5°C, 6°C, 11°C, 17°C, 22°C, 26°C, 29°C, 29°C, 24°C, 18°C, 12°C, and 10°C Jan–Dec. After 10 yr, the seeds still have desirable germination abilities. Average moisture content before sealing was about 12%; it is now 7–8%. Average germination rate is about 90%. Seedlings

derived from the germinated seeds grow well in the field.

The characteristics of this preservation method are

1. Well-sealed conditions. The ampule was sealed by melting the glass tip, the relative humidity was very low and, with adequate silica gel, continuously becomes lower and lower.

Rice seed samples in glass ampules. Hunan, China, 1987.

2. Ease in operating. It is very easy to seal the ampule vials using a bunsen burner and a pair of tweezers.
3. Ease in keeping. The ampule is made of glass, which cannot be affected by moisture, insects, and rats. It can be stored in normal conditions.
4. Low cost. The ampules are very cheap. One 2-ml ampule can store 20-30 rice seeds, enough to use for breeding parents. A 20-ml ampule bottle can hold 500 rice seeds.
5. Use for other crops. Glass ampules can be used for other small-seed crops, such as wheat, vegetables, and rapeseeds. □

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Response of new rice varieties to N

M.S.Maskina, yadvinder-singh and Bijay-Singh, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

Rice variety PR106 covers about 80% of the area under rice in Punjab. Recently, yield at experimental farms and in farmers' fields have dropped markedly. Susceptibility of cultivars to a number of plant diseases was found to be the major reason. Two new varieties with high yield potential — PR108 and PR109 — are more resistant to plant pathogens. Because Punjab soils are inherently deficient in organic matter N, a substantial response of the three varieties to applied N is expected.

We studied the response of the three varieties to four N levels during 1986 summer. Treatments were laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. Soils (pH 8.4 EC 0.16 dS/m, 0.30%

Grain yield, N uptake, and yield parameters of 3 rice varieties at different levels of N application, Punjab, India, 1986 summer.

Variety	No N	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	150 kg N/ha	Mean
<i>Grain yield (t/ha)</i>					
PR106	2.7	5.5	5.8	6.2	5.0
PR108	3.3	6.0	6.3	6.7	5.6
PR109	3.1	5.7	6.1	6.4	5.3
Mean	3.0	5.7	6.1	6.4	
LSD (P=0.05): N levels = 0.27, varieties = 0.31, NXV = ns					
<i>Effective tillers/plant</i>					
PR106	8.4	9.4	9.7	10.7	9.6
PR108	8.5	9.5	11.5	11.9	10.4
PR109	8.7	9.1	10.6	11.5	10.0
Mean	8.5	9.3	10.6	11.4	
LSD (P=0.05): N levels = 0.5, varieties = 0.4, NXV = ns					
<i>Filled spikelets/panicle</i>					
PR106	92	97	99	112	100
PR108	109	115	122	127	118
PR109	94	107	109	117	107
Mean	98	106	110	119	
LSD (P=0.05): N levels = 7, varieties = 8, NXV = ns					
<i>N uptake</i>					
PR106	39	106	125	138	102
PR108	61	127	140	150	120
PR109	53	113	132	142	110
Mean	51	115	132	143	
LSD (P=0.05): N levels = 9, varieties = 8, NXV = ns					